

Phrasal verbs and their role in English

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Abstract

Phrasal verbs or particle verbs are one of the most idiosyncratic features of the English language, as well as of other Germanic languages, such as German or Dutch. They pose many problems for non-native speakers, because their meanings have to be learned separately from the meanings of their verbal bases (give vs. give up), given that the union of the two elements of the compound (the verb and the particle) very often gives rise to new non-compositional forms very similar to idioms.

Keywords: Phraseology; Phraseological units; genealogy,; phenomenon; heritage, culture, evolvment, segments, realizationn

Роль фразовых глаголов в английском языке

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Отрывок

Фразовые глаголы или глаголы-частицы являются одной из наиболее характерных особенностей английского языка, а также других германских языков, таких как немецкий или голландский. Они создают много проблем для неносителей языка, поскольку их значения приходится изучать отдельно от значений их глагольных основ (давать vs. отказываться), учитывая, что объединение двух элементов сложного слова (глагола и частицы) очень часто порождает новые некомпозиционные формы, очень похожие на фразеологизмы.

Ключевые слова: фразеология; фразеологические единицы; генеалогия; явление; наследие, культура, развитие, сегменты, реализация

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Izoh

Fraze fe'llar yoki zarracha fe'llar ingliz tilining, shuningdek, nemis yoki golland kabi boshqa german tillarining eng o'ziga xos xususiyatlaridan biridir. Ular ona tili bo'lmaganlar uchun juda ko'p muammolar tug'diradi, chunki birikmaning ikki elementi (fe'l va zarracha) birlashishi hisobga olinsa, ularning ma'nolarini og'zaki asoslari ma'nolaridan alohida o'rganish kerak (berish va voz kechish).) ko'pincha idiomalarga juda o'xshash yangi kompozitsiyasiz shakllarni keltirib chiqaradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Frazеologiya; Frazеologik birliklar; nasabnoma,; hodisa; meros, madaniyat, rivojlanish, segmentlar, amalga oshirish

Phrasal verbs can be said to be formed by the combination of a verb and an adverb or a preposition. In some cases, it is a combination of all the three parts of speech – verb, adverb and preposition. Though each of these parts of speech have different functions, they play the role of the verb when they are put together. They can also act as a phrase and that is why these verbs are called phrasal verbs.

Definition of a Phrasal Verb

The Oxford Learner's Dictionary defines a phrasal verb as “a verb combined with an adverb or a preposition, or sometimes both, to give a new meaning, for example, ‘go in for’, ‘win over’ and ‘see to’.” According to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary, a phrasal verb is defined as “a phrase (such as take off or look down on) that combines a verb with a preposition or adverb or both, and that functions as a verb whose meaning is different from the combined meanings of the individual words.” The Cambridge Dictionary defines a phrasal verb as “a phrase that consists of a verb with a preposition or adverb or both, the meaning of which is different from the meaning of its separate parts.”

Types of Phrasal Verbs

Phrasal verbs can be divided into four main types or rather two main categories based on how they behave when used in sentences. They are:

Intransitive Phrasal Verbs

Intransitive phrasal verbs behave exactly like intransitive verbs. They do not require an object to complete the sentence they are used in or make sense of the context.

For example:

My car broke down all of a sudden while driving through the ghat section.

It has been years since we met, we should definitely catch up.

Separable Phrasal Verbs

Separable phrasal verbs include transitive phrasal verbs which have the characteristic property of separating the phrasal verb with the object in between. There is, however, a word order which should be taken into account when separating the phrasal verb.

For example:

I am not the kind of person who holds all of this against you.

Dhiraj is the one who is taking care of the applications for gold loan. Can you please hand it over to him?

Inseparable Phrasal Verbs

Inseparable phrasal verbs, as the name suggests, cannot be separated from each other and have to be used together, no matter what.

For example:

You will have to account for all the losses that have been incurred.

Harish was asked to check out of the hotel before 9 p.m. on Tuesday.

How to Use Phrasal Verbs?

As fun and interesting as it is to use phrasal verbs, there are a few pointers you have to keep in mind when using them in your daily communication. Following a particular word order and conjugating it to represent the tense of the sentence are the two things you have to learn and put into practice.

Conjugating Phrasal Verbs

As far as the conjugation part is concerned, all you have to remember is to employ the same rules of conjugation you would if the verb stands by itself. When the phrasal verb is used as a main verb, you have to conjugate the verb alone according to the respective tense and not change the preposition in the phrasal verb.

For example:

Kate let me down when she did not show up for my court hearing.

Some phrasal verbs will always require to be separated by the direct object in between.

For example:

We are very glad that we have you around during this difficult time.

When noun phrases act as the object, it can also be placed in between the verb and the preposition.

For example:

He was asked to leave all of it out for approval.

Examples of Phrasal Verbs

Phrasal verbs are most often a topic that confuses a lot of people, especially second language learners and new learners of the language. Since the multiple words used in a phrasal verb have different meanings and have a completely different meaning when used together, they end up being a slightly puzzling topic for some.

Phrasal verbs can be conjugated to suit the tense of the sentence and can be used like a normal verb. Here are a few examples of phrasal verbs. Identify how many of them you know and how often you use them in your regular communication.

Give up – combination of a verb (give) and a preposition (up)

Individually, the verb ‘give’ means to give something to someone and the preposition ‘up’ shows the position of some object. The magic happens or the confusion begins when both the verb and the preposition are used together. The phrasal ‘give up’ means to surrender or to stop making an effort in doing something.

Let us look at how the phrasal verb ‘give up’ can be conjugated to represent the different verb forms in English.

Simple Past Form

The captain gave up at the last quarter.

Infinitive Form

It was not easy for the coach to give up trying to encourage the team even in such a hopeless situation.

Gerund Form

Giving up is not the solution to the problem, it is just the easiest choice.

Past Participle Form

I have given up on them.

For more examples, check out Phrasal Verbs List.

Check Your Understanding of Phrasal Verbs

Fill in the blanks by choosing the most appropriate phrasal verbs from the list of phrasal verbs given below. Conjugate them to suit the tense of the sentence.

(stand for, narrow down, hold on, run into, check out, go through, fall apart, pull off, fill in, hold against)

1. Make sure you _____ of the hotel at the right time, else they will charge you extra.
2. Levin was asked to _____ for Suresh.
3. _____ the whole itinerary before you make a decision.
4. Tom and Jerry _____ after their last meeting.

5. Please _____ for a minute, I forgot to take my car keys.
6. It is not good to _____ such a silly issue _____ her for so many years.
7. Do you think Andraeah would be able to _____ it _____ all by herself?
8. We have _____ the possibilities of them finding us.
9. Do you know who we _____ on our way here?
10. Nelson Mandela _____ for the rights of his people.

Check your answers here.

1. Make sure you check out of the hotel at the right time, else they will charge you extra.
2. Levin was asked to fill in for Suresh.
3. Go through the whole itinerary before you make a decision.
4. Tom and Jerry fell apart after their last meeting.
5. Please hold on for a minute, I forgot to take my car keys.

6. It is not good to hold such a silly issue against her for so many years.
7. Do you think Andreah would be able to pull it off all by herself?
8. We have narrowed down the possibilities of them finding us.
9. Do you know who we ran into on our way here?
10. Nelson Mandela stood up for the rights of his people.

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